

List of Primary Studies

This appendix provides the list of 41 primary studies analyzed in the multivocal literature review.

Table A – List of analyzed academic literature studies

- [A1] V. Peñarroja, V. Orenge, A. Zornoza, J. Sánchez, P. Ripoll, How team feedback and team trust influence information processing and learning in virtual teams: A moderated mediation model. *Computers in Human Behavior*, v. 48, p. 9-16, ISSN 0747-5632, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2015.01.034>, 2015.
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- [A20] C. Siebra, L. Sodre, J. Quintino, F. Q. B. da Silva, A. L. M. Santos, Collaborative Feedback and Its Effects on Software Teams, in *IEEE Software*, vol. 37, no. 5, pp. 85-93, Sept.-Oct. 2020, doi:10.1109/MS.2019.2946565, 2020.
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Table B – List of analyzed gray literature studies.

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